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Karan Singh

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From the Editor

It gives me pleasure to present the wide range of research featured in this volume. The first paper is on Yaudheya copper coins, providing a new classification of this series of ancient India. We then take a look at the early Islamic period of Iran, and the role played by countermarked Arab-Sasanian coins. We also have a report on the first-ever hoard of Burmese coins to be found outside Myanmar (formerly Burma). Finally, this volume provides a detailed look at the transition to machine-made coinage in late-19th century Afghanistan.

We wish to thank Spink & Son for graciously sponsoring the editing of the journal for 2021. I look forward to receiving submissions from members interested in showcasing the numismatic research they have undertaken.

Karan Singh

COUNTERMARKED ARAB-SASANIAN COPPER COINS OF JAHROM

Seyed Omid Mohammadi and Saeed Soleimani

Arab-Sasanian copper coins bearing the 'Jahrom' countermark have been briefly introduced by multiple sources. However, the rarity of such specimens made it hard for researchers to study these countermarks properly. Recently, the authors had the opportunity to examine a collection of these coins thoroughly and identify multiple new countermarks for the first time. This research is dedicated to the introduction and classification of these new countermarks. We also hope to answer some questions along the way: What was the role and importance of Jahrom city in the pre-Islamic era of Iran? What evidence of pre-Islamic civilisations reside in the territory? What was the meaning and use of these countermarks? Who was possibly responsible, and what was the reason behind countermarking these coins?

City of Jahrom

Jahrom is the capital of Jahrom county in Fars province of modern-day Iran. Shiraz and Fasa surround this county from the north, Fasa and Zarrin-Dasht from the east, Lar and Firuzabad from the south, and Firuzabad from the west. Jahrom county consists of Jahrom, Khavaran, Bab Anar, and Qotbabad cities, and four administrative divisions (*bakhsh*): Central, Khafz, Simakan, and Kordian. The location of Jahrom is shown in the map in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Mints of Fars province in early Islamic Iran

Historical background

The county of Jahrom is historically and archaeologically rich, with numerous remains of ancient castles, buildings, and other historical sites. However, very few archaeological excavations have been undertaken in the region, leaving us with little to no information about this territory's history. Most of what we have is from written sources, the silence of which leads to a dark era after the Arab invasion of this part of Iran.

We know that Jahrom was a prosperous city even before Ardashir Papakan, and Jahrom, Fasa and Darabjird were thriving cities (*ma'mur*) before Shiraz (Hakim 1987: 536). Jahrom is also mentioned as the residence of princes (Ibn al-Balkhi, Le Strange and Nicholson 1984: 115). In this era, Fars was divided into five districts (*kura*): Istakhr, Shapur Khwarrah, Ardashir Khwarrah, Darabjird and Kavād Khwarrah. Jahrom, part of the Darabjird district (Taghavi 2008: 16), is mentioned in various sources (Ibn al-Balkhi 1984: 115; Le Strange 1905: 254) as an impregnable

fortress with high military advantage and a strategic location to retreat to after possible failures in battles (Toofan 2002: 50).

Different origins and meanings are suggested for the word 'Jahrom' or 'Gahrom'. Kasravi suggests that it means 'a warm place' (1974: 273-283). This concept is in line with the city's hot climate and the intolerable heat in the summer (Athari 2012: 22). Furthermore, in the story of Bahram Gur (Bahram V) in Ferdowsi's *Shahnameh*, Jahrom is mentioned as a "waterless plain" (Ferdowsi and Davis and Nafisi 2016: 703).

There is no information about the exact location of the ancient city. In our research, we tried to locate the remains of castles and other historically significant sites, with the hope of obtaining a rough idea of the city's founding centre, by plotting all these sites in one map (Fig. 2). We should mention that the lack of archaeological excavations in the area makes it extremely difficult to date these historical remains and sites. Thus, unfortunately, when we talk about pre-Islamic sites and castles, we cannot determine the exact period.

Fig. 2 shows that the ancient city's central core may not be far from its current location. The Jahrom plain lies in the Zagros fold and thrust belt, and Alborz-Kuh ('high mountain'),¹ working as a natural fence to the south and southeast of the city, gave it a strategic and defensive advantage. The high density of historical sites and numerous remains of castles in the area confirms this, especially Castles 10 and 11, two great fortresses built specifically in impregnable mountainous areas. Written sources mention the distance between Fasa to Jahrom to be about ten leagues (60 km) (Istakhri 1963: 117), and from Shiraz to Jahrom to be about 30 leagues (180 km) (Jayhani 1989: 110), which is compatible with the current location of the city.

One of the first times we see the name of Jahrom in the written sources is in a book written in AH 232, which writes: "*Rasatigh* (villages) of Darabjird [:] Kurm (Karm?), Jahram (Jahrom), Neyriz, Al-Bastejan, Al-Abjard, Al-Andian, Juyom, Furj, Tarum, and Tamestan" (Ibn Khordadbeh: 46). *Mukhtasar al-Buldan*, written in AH 290, provides similar information (Ibn al-Faqih al-Hamadani: 16). Some sources of the AH 4th century mention Jahrom as *rostaq* (village) (Ibn Hawqal: 33), though later sources refer to it as *qasbah*,² with the emphasis on the fact that it was once a city (Shirvani: 754-855). At the end of the AH 4th century, Jahrom, turned from a village to a *qasbah*, again becomes a city, but never returns to its former glory.

The main question is: why are there no traces of Jahrom, once an important city in the Achaemenid and Sasanian periods, in written sources from the Islam conquest till the AH 4th century? Why is it merely mentioned as one of Darabjird's villages afterwards? We do not have a clear answer yet. Perhaps the destruction of the city during the Arab invasion (or consequent events) is the reason. Most sources mention the year AH 23 as the year of the Arab conquest of Fars (Tabari 1973: Vol. 5, 2006). We also know that Uthman ibn Abi al-As al-Thaqafi, ordered by Umar ibn al-Khaṭṭāb, established a base and garrison in Tawwaj and orchestrated attacks on other cities of Fars (Hinds: 43). The order in which cities fell to the Arabs is mentioned as "Shahpur (Bishapur), Jarrah,³ Kazerun, Nobandegan (Nobandegan), Arrajan, Shiraz, Siniz,⁴ Darabjird, Jahrom, and Fasa" (Al-Baladhuri: 259). Sources mention that Umar appointed Sariyah bin Zuneim to attack the Darabjird *kura*, including Darab, Fasa, and Jahrom. However, after multiple unsuccessful attacks on Jahrom, he failed to capture the city due to the rallying of Persian forces behind the city gates. Having captured Rewshahr (Bushehr) in the year AH 23, Uthman marched to Jahrom to confront the Persian defenders (*ibid.*: 260). Finally, he was able to besiege and seize the city. Some believe that the final battle took place somewhere to the east of Castle 7 and the west of Castle 8; which is why this area is called *Shohada* ('martyrs') to this day (Toofan: 54).

Fig. 2. Historical sites of Jahrom district from pre-Islamic and early Islamic eras (based on Google Maps)

In this map, the city of Jahrom (marked with 📍), pre-Islamic remains, and historical sites, including fortresses and castles (called Ghale Gabri 🏰), Chahar Taqis (🔥), ancient dams and water dykes (🌊), pre-Islamic houses/ graves⁵ (called Khane Gabri 🏠) and minars⁶ (🗼), are shown with exact locations (Athari 2012: 510-556)

- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| 1) Tabar castle (Khorsha) | 9) Qadamgah | 17) Haj Sharifi castle's Khane Gabri |
| 2) Mok castle | 10) pre-Islamic castle of Ghalat | 18) Leh Janbaz (Leh Jamasp) castle |
| 3) Zuhair-Shir chahartaqi (Baba-Arab) | 11) pre-Islamic castle of Alborz mountain (Mihrak castle) | 19) pre-Islamic castle of Badenjan |
| 4) pre-Islamic castle of Khane Nahr | 12) Sohrun minaret | 20) Tang-e Zafran Khane Gabri |
| 5) Band-o-Bast (Band-o-Bost) dam | 13) Nargesi castle | 21) historical remains of Borju |
| 6) pre-Islamic castle of Par, near Rudkhane Shur | 14) Tadevan Khane Gabri (pre-Islamic house) | 22) historical remains of Rasha mountain |
| 7) pre-Islamic castle of Jovin or Par-e Hana | 15) Tadevan castle and Tal-e Naghare Khane | 23) Barat castle |
| 8) pre-Islamic castle of Dameshkaft mountain | 16) Khalu Khane Gabri | 24) Ismail castle |
| | | 25) pre-Islamic castle of Sarbah |

It is noteworthy that the sequence in which these cities fell – Bushehr, then Darab, and Jahrom – is consistent across the various sources. Ibn Balkhi mentions AH 20 as the year that Uthman departed to conquer Darabjird *kura* and then Fasa, Jahrom, and Fatisjan, and AH 23 as the year in which he succeeded. Ibn Balkhi also points out that some cities, including Darabjird and Fasa, surrendered with no bloodshed and agreed to pay *jizya* and taxes (Ibn al-Balkhi, Le Strange & Nicholson 1984: 115). However, Jahrom was not one of these and was conquered by war (Hinds: 46). So, by taking into account the resistance of the Persian army in Jahrom, the siege of the city, and the fact that it was one of the last cities to be conquered, it seems that AH 23 is the year that Muslims conquered Jahrom (Ibn al-Athir 2006: 1548).

Coins with countermarks

We recently had the chance to study a collection of Arab-Sasanian countermarked copper coins from the district of Jahrom. These specimens are rich in information due to the variety of countermarks and their rarity. The study of such coins can lead to a fresh perspective on this relatively undocumented period of history. In this research, we analyse 20 specimens,⁷ thereby introducing multiple countermarks for the first time.

The discussed coins are Arab-Sasanian copper coins, classified as Gyselen Type 10 (Gyselen 2000: 125) and Treadwell Phase B coinage (Treadwell 2008: 338), all struck at Darabjird mint and bearing the mint-name and a date. The coins depict the royal bust of a Sasanian king on the obverse, with Pahlavi legends *GDH "xvarrah"* behind his head and *'pzwt' "abzud"* in front, meaning 'May xvarrah increase'. There is also *bismillah* in Arabic in the second quarter of the margin, meaning 'In the Name of God'. On the reverse, there is a fire altar without attendants; to the right, *DA* in Pahlavi, an abbreviation of Darabjird mint, and to the left, we can see the date, also in Pahlavi. There is another *'pzwt' "abzud"* in the second quarter of the margin, and G10b specimens have an additional word *بركة (Barkat)* in Arabic, meaning 'benediction', in the third quarter.

There are reports of these coins with different dates. Year 47 (probably Post-Yazdigird Era, AH 79),⁸ 60, 67, and 68 Yazdigird Era (AH 72, 79, and 80) are known. Although other Darabjird copper coins exist bearing the year 72 YE (AH 84) and AH 94 (with Arabic date) (Gyselen 2000: 89), they are different types and out of the scope of this research. Coins bearing the year 47 were first presumed to use the YE calendar, coinciding with AH 58 (Album and Goodwin 2002: 57). However, new research conducted by Album (2011: 28) and Treadwell show

that it is more probable that this date uses the PYE calendar. If we accept this interpretation, it means that two coins with dates 47 and 67 are both struck in the same year (AH 79) in one mint, which is odd. Furthermore, accepting this hypothesis means that a sudden change of calendar happened in AH 79 in Darabjird, for which we do not have any explanation.

There are also small distinctive features on these two coin types. In the coins of year 47, the face is slimmer and a little longer. Furthermore, in the coins of year 47, unlike years 67 and 68, the crown is connected to the wings through two narrow lines. The word *بركة* 'Barkat' is also written in the third quarter reverse margin of years 67 and 68, which we can be used distinctively to identify this type among coins with illegible dates. Although comparing the weights of these coins might not be precise due to copper coins' high corrosion, the average weights of these two dates are also different. Coins of year 47 (14 samples) weigh an average of 3.64 g, while coins of year 67 (13 samples) weigh about 2.87 g on average (Treadwell 2008: 344). In fact, both interpretations for the year 47 have some inconsistencies, and accepting either of them raises problems. This date seems to be an unsolved riddle.

Interestingly, all 20 specimens we analysed were in very worn condition with a smooth and sometimes glossy surface. The motifs were barely visible. On the other hand, the countermarks were sharp and in good condition, which points out that the coins' erosion is not only because of the passing of time and effects of soil or corrosion. These coins most probably were in circulation for a long time and were withdrawn from circulation due to their worn condition. They were used as ready metal planchets, countermarked to guarantee their validity, and returned to circulation again. In examples like Coin 7, no motif is visible, and only the planchet is left of the base coin. Countermarks found on these coins are listed in Table A. Only two of these eight countermarks have been recorded before.

Table A. List of countermarks

Type	Countermark	Legend	Meaning	No. of pieces in sample of 20
1		جهرم in Arabic	Jahrom, name of the city	20
2		ghlwm in Pahlavi	Jahrom, name of the city	7
3		جايز in Arabic	Ja'iz (legal, lawful, current)	1
4.1		lwb'k in Pahlavi	رواج، رایج Raväg (current)	5
4.2		lwb'k? in Pahlavi	رواج، رایج Raväg (current)	1
4.3		lwb'k in Pahlavi	رواج، رایج Raväg (current)	1

5		الله in Arabic	Lillah (for God)	1
6		جيد in Arabic	Jayyid (nice, good, valid)	1

Countermark 1

Countermark 1 is the name of the city of Jahrom: جهرم in Arabic. Walker was the first to report this countermark (1967: pl. cxlvi). He successfully read the legend, but had difficulty interpreting it. He thought that جهرم is a faulty form of چهارم ('the fourth'). After him, Gaube solved this puzzle (1973: 116), then Mochiri (1986) and Curiel (1984: 12) also wrote about this countermark. As mentioned above, these countermarks are struck on very worn coins, so the countermark's exact position may not be of importance. However, according to Table B, we can see that most of them were struck on the first half of the obverse, usually near the edges and away from the royal bust.

Table B. The location of Countermark 1 on the coins

	The quarter containing the countermark				
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Unknown
Obverse	6	7	2	1	3
Reverse				1	

Countermark 1 seems to be the main countermark in this series, as all 20 specimens bear this countermark. There are also different types and multiple versions of calligraphy for this specific countermark. We identified at least six different dies for this countermark in our sample of 20, which shows that a significant number of coins were countermarked. Different types of Countermark 1 are shown in Table C.

Table C. Different varieties of Countermark 1

Countermark	Variety	No. of pieces in 20
	1.a	3
	1.b	2
	1.c	9

	1.d	2
	1.e	2
	1.f	1

We can see that different varieties have distinctive features. Paying attention to the letter "ر" helps in most cases. Types 1.c and 1.d have different dimensions and sizes, which might not be evident in the illustrations. The countermark frame in Type 1.c is more oversized with an 8x6 mm dimension, while 1.d has a smaller frame of 6x4 mm. This smaller dimension has led to the compression of the text, and there is less space between letters, paying attention to which helps us identify these two types in pictures. Type 1.f is also noteworthy because it lacks delicacy, and the calligraphy looks crude and not as beautiful as the other varieties.

Countermark 2

Countermark 2 depicts the name of Jahrom city again, this time in Pahlavi. This form of "ghlwm" گهروم is consistent with what we see on other copper coins minted in Jahrom (Gyselen Types 54, 107 and 108). There is also a silver drachm of Qatari bin al-Fuja'a year AH 75 (Fig. 3a) with the same mint-name. However, there were no reports of this name used in a countermark until now. This countermark and other examples in Pahlavi remind us that although Arabs conquered the area, the people's primary language remained Pahlavi. So there was a need for these Pahlavi countermarks, beside Arabic versions, to communicate with local people and inform them about such coins' validity.

Countermark 2 helps us inspect the city's old name and its pronunciation. The group of Islamic historians who recorded names of cities with pronunciations, including Istakhri (1963: 107), Ibn Hawqal (1966: 33), Ibn Khordadbeh (1967: 46), Yaqut al-Hamawi (2004: 113), Ibn al-Faqih (1970: 203), and others, all recorded the city's name with short /a/ (fatha) as جهرم (Jahram). With the arrival of European travellers to Iran, we see this word written with short /o/ (damma) as Jahrom in their travel journals in the AH 11th century (Afshar [Sistani] 1999: 265).

Fig. 3a. Arab-Sasanian drachm of Qatari bin al-Fuja'a, Darabjird-Jahrom mint, AH 75, 3.99 g⁹

Fig. 3b. Line-drawing of Jahrom mint-name seen in Fig. 3a

Although we do not know the exact reason for this duality in pronunciation among the works of historians, with the help of this countermark (and of course, other coins mentioned earlier), we know that the standard pronunciation of this name in the AH 1st century was definitely جهروم (Jahrum) or جهرم (Jahrom), with both forms (with short or long /o/) being correct and common. Interestingly, both these forms can be seen eight centuries later, on the coins of Uzun Hasan and Rustam of the Aq Qoyunlu dynasty (Figs. 4a and 5a). The countermark in Fig. 4a depicts the city's name the same way as the Arabic Countermark 1 in the form of جهرم (Jahrom). However, Fig. 5a shows the name as جهروم (Jahrum). Both countermarks have clear dates and are applied only within a 30-year range.

Fig. 4a. 'Jahrom' countermark of Aq Qoyunlu, Uzun Hasan, AH 872 on a Timurid tanka of Abdullah, Samarqand, 4.81 g¹⁰

۸۷۲ عدل حسين بيک، جهرم،
(Adl Hasan Beik, Jahrom, 872)

Fig. 4b. Line drawing of countermark seen in Fig. 4a

Fig. 5a. Countermark of Aq Qoyunlu, Rustam, 'Jahrum', AH 899 on a Timurid tanka of AH 898, 5.05 g¹¹

۸۹۹ عدل سلطان رستم، جهرم،
(Adl Sultan Rustam, Jahrum, 899)

Fig. 5b. Line drawing of countermark seen in Fig. 5a

Countermark 2 also has some crude versions. This countermark is the second most common among this group. The exact locations of this countermark on the specimens are shown in Table D. Although we do not have enough samples to reach a definitive conclusion, it seems that this countermark is mostly struck on the reverse of the coins, which is the opposite side of Countermark 1.

Table D. The location of Countermark 2 on the coins

	The quarter containing the countermark				
	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Unknown
Obverse		1			2
Reverse			2	2	

Countermark 3

Countermark 3 is the Arabic word جائز *Ja'iz* (lawful, legal, permitted, allowable). This word is used in the legends of some other copper coins of that era, including Gyselen Type 4 of Bishapur, numerous Arab-Byzantine AE coins (Mitchiner 1977: 55), and some Umayyad copper coins. The *Ja'iz* countermark also exists on various Arab-Sasanian silver drachms, mostly in the margin, but such a countermark with this calligraphy has never been reported on Arab-Sasanian copper coins. The calligraphy of this countermark is different and uncommon. It seems that the letter "ز" is located at the bottom of the letter "ي", which is odd, but it might just be the style of the engraver. In any case, the countermark is so clear and sharp that it leaves no doubt about its reading.

Countermark 3 is only struck on one of the samples (Coin 7) and precisely in the middle of the coin, maybe due to the complete lack of motifs. This specific coin is so worn that only the copper planchet is left. That is why all the countermarks are struck together on one side only of the coin.

Countermark 4

Countermark 4, and its sub-categories, all seem to depict the word *lwb'k* in Pahlavi. This word *Raväg* ('current', رواج رواج) shows the validity of the coin in monetary circulation. Thus, it also points out the coins' legitimacy, leading us to interpret 'legal' and 'lawful' meanings. This term is well-known and occurs on numerous Arab-Sasanian copper coins. Gyselen reports 18 coin types mentioning this word (2000: 95). However, such a term used as a countermark, with various calligraphy types, was unknown to us.

Countermark 4.3 is a clear and common form of this term that we see on numerous other coins. Countermark 4.1 is another form of this term also known to us, engraved beautifully and with precision. However, there is still doubt about Countermark 4.2. This countermark (on Coin 6) is similar to 4.1, but with fewer letters. They might be the same word, or it can merely be *l'yk*? "رایج", a Pahlavi-Arabic hybrid form of the term. The final letter in this sample is also odd, which might be due to the countermark being double-struck. Can it be a mistake of the engraver, or is it a new countermark? We only have one sample of this countermark, and it is not enough to reach a conclusion.

Group countermarks of No. 4 are usually seen alongside جهرم, Countermark 1, sometimes beside it (Coins 4, 5, and 7) and other times on the opposite side (Coin 6). Due to the small number of these countermark samples, we did not analyse their exact location. Some were applied on the obverse, and the same number on the reverse.

Countermark 5

Countermark 5 is the word *lillah* in Arabic, meaning 'for the god', which was first reported by Walker (1967: pl. cxlvi) and then Curiel as a countermark on copper coins (1984: 12). This term is a part of the Kharijites' motto and was used as a countermark on the silver drachms of the Kirman area. Mochiri suggests that the Kharijites were responsible for both Countermarks 1 and 5. He believes that Kharajite probably had control over Jahrom city sometime after AH 68 (687 CE) (Mochiri 1986: 61). Although the calligraphy is very similar to that of Kharijites on silver drachms, there is a chance that it is merely a religious motto. This countermark occurs only once on our analysed samples (Coin 1, dated 47), on the reverse at eleven o'clock.

Countermark 6

Countermark 6 shows the Arabic word "جيد" *jayyid*, meaning 'good', 'nice', or 'valid'. This term occurs in the second quarter of the margin on Arab-Sasanian drachms in the name of Yazdگرد. However, it was never reported as a countermark on copper coins. Only one example of this countermark occurs in our samples (Coin 7), in the coin's margin. The ratio of Countermark 5 (*lillah*) specimens to the whole group is not enough to conclude that these countermarks belong to the Kharijite movement. However, it is not easy to reject this hypothesis either. Keeping the city's strategic location and

defensive advantage in mind, it is logical that Kharijites controlled the city for some time. We know that Qatari bin al-Fuja'a struck silver drachms at Jahrom mint in AH 75, and the mint name is so clear and full that it leaves no doubt. Although the time of these two incidents might seem close, it is worth bearing in mind that these countermarks were struck after AH 80, and judging from the worn condition of the specimens, probably years after this date.

Tabar castle (Castle 1 in Fig. 2) is also of importance. Built in the Umayyad era (Le Strange 1905: 254), the castle is located 40 km to the east of the city. This castle had offered refuge to rebel groups and fugitive leaders from the time it was built (AH 73) until Naser al-Din Shah (AH 1294) (Fasā'ī: 333). The unique geographic features of the castle are the reason. It is located on top of a high mountain with the same name, a mountain with loose rocks and a hazardous steep slope. Only one narrow route to the castle and the necessity of using rope, created a great hideout with strategic advantage. According to Ibn Balkhi's description, no one could conquer this castle even with arms. The castle was built by Khorsha (خورشه),¹² the sub-governor (*amil*) of Jahrom under Umayyad caliphs. He rebelled against the governor (*wali*) of Fars, Muhammad ibn Yusuf al-Thaqafi, brother of Al-Hajjaj ibn Yusuf, and took refuge in this castle (Ibn Al-Balkhi 1984: 157). This incident happened sometime in AH 75-95 (Gundelfinger and Verkinderen 2020: 320). It is hard to say whether these countermarks are related to this rebellion or not. However, the coincidence of these two incidents is worth considering.

The only thing we know for sure is that sometime after AH 80 in Jahrom, Arabs withdrew worn copper coins of Darabjird mint (which were probably current in the district) from circulation, countermarked these coins, and re-entered them into the monetary cycle. We support Gyselen's hypothesis that these countermarks were for local circulation. Although coins bearing Countermark 1 reported by Gyselen were very limited (2 samples out of 40), this countermark's abundance in the current study (20 out of the 20 specimens studied) shows that these marks were more probably used to legitimise the local circulation of such coins.

We add one small detail to complete this hypothesis. Gyselen believed that Arabic countermarks, specifically Countermark 1, were used because the mint name of the coins (*DA*) was in Pahlavi and unusual to Arabs. Seeing bilingual Arabic-Pahlavi forms of these countermarks (Countermarks 1 and 2) together, we now know that this might not be the whole truth. The purpose of these countermarks was to introduce these once worn coins to the people of Jahrom, both Arab and Iranian, which is why they needed to use both languages common in the region.

Conclusion

We have analysed and classified countermarks on Arab-Sasanian copper coins of Jahrom, and introduced four new countermarks not known to us on Arab-Sasanian *pashiz* coins before. We also classified different styles of Arabic countermark ۱ (Countermark 1) into at least six different types, and this great variety shows that a large number of coins were countermarked. Furthermore, these sharp countermarks on worn copper coins prove that these marks were probably applied to re-enter these worn coins into local circulation.

In our research, not only did we encounter countermarks with city names (Countermarks 1 and 2), which show the locality of such examples, but we also saw a different class of countermarks used for re-validating and re-entering coins into circulation (Countermarks 3, 4 and 6). Additionally, the Arabic-Pahlavi bilinguality of these countermarks is impressive and unique. Even so, our knowledge of Jahrom in the dark period of history after the Islamic conquest is minimal. We hope that archaeological excavations in the region, and possibly historical and numismatic discoveries, shine some light on this ancient region's history and solve some of these riddles in the future.

Coin images

Coin 1: Countermarks 1 and 5
Year 47, 3.53 g

Coin 2: Countermark 1
Year 68, 3.03 g

Coin 3: Countermarks 1 and 2
3.02 g

Coin 4: Countermarks 1, 2, and 4.1
3.34 g

Coin 5: Countermarks 1 and 4.3
3.60 g

Coin 6: Countermarks 1 and 4.2
Year 68, 3.91 g

Coin 7: Countermarks 1, 2, 3, 4.1, 6
and an incomplete countermark

References

1. Not to be confused with Alborz mountain.
2. Usually multiple structures behind a defensive wall.
3. Jareh is currently located 50 km to the southeast of Kazerun.
4. Senez, Si-Niz or Shiniz, is a port currently located in Deylam county of Bushehr province.
5. Due to their hard-to-reach locations in the mountains, some believe these are catacombs, while others suggest these were houses based on the water wells found nearby.
6. *Mils* or *minars* are tower-like structures used as observation towers, fire temples, or more likely as fire markers to guide travellers on the roads.
7. The illustrated coins are from the authors' collection.
8. Ilisch, Peus (Frankfurt) Auction 363, 26 April 2000, Lot 5556.
9. ANS 1956.137.80 American Numismatic Society, accessed January 4, 2021, <http://numismatics.org/collection/1956.137.80>.
10. Authors' collection.
11. Triskeles Auctions, Sale 20, Lot 784.
12. Known by many names, including Khurshah (خورشاده), Khurushah, Kharashah, and other variations.

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